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Research Article

**A TRANSVERSE STUDY TO ASSESS THE HEPATITIS B & C
VIRUS (HBV & HCV) BURDEN IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF
SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC STATUS OF THE PATIENTS****¹Dr. Beenish Malik, ²Dr. Aimen Mahmood, ³Dr. Noreen Fatima**¹Pmdc 94003-P, BHU Chak Sada Gujrat²Pmdc: 93197-P, BHU Chak No. 12 SB/ Sargodha³Pmdc: 93270-P, THQ Liaqat Pur**Abstract**

Objective: The main aim of this research work is to conclude the burden of infection of HBV & HCV in accordance with the social & economic condition.

Methodology: This transverse research work carried out at Medicine Department of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from November 2016 to October 2017. All patients with infection of HBV & HCV from every age group and gender were the part of this research work. The interview of all the patients carried out to know about the previous history of operations, history of needle pricking, shaving from barbers & history of birth to check the risk factors transmission. The patients also told about their social and economic condition. A special organized Performa was in use to record the gathered information.

Results: Two hundred patients were the part of this case study. A large quantity of the patients (110) belonged to the age group of thirty-one to forty-five year of age. Male patients were dominant in this case study and constituting sixty percent of the whole amount. All the male patients had a previous history of having shaved from barbers as well as extra utilization of the needles were frequent in both genders constituting 125 of the total patients. Infection of HCV was very common with a seventy-one percentage of the patients. Most of the patients of these infections were poor people of the communities (forty-eight percent). Patients of low social and economic status were more prone to the infection of HCV. There was no significant disparity in the infection of HBV in accordance with the social and economic condition.

Conclusion: Conclusions displayed that low economic and social condition had an association with the infection of HCV. The socioeconomic condition is not a direct factor of risk for HCV & HBV but it is the cause of the creation of many other risk aspects.

Keywords: Hepatitis, Impact, Economic, Patient, Performa, Aspect, Transmission, Needle.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis due to the virus is a dangerous health issue in the whole world including Pakistan & India. There are 5 types of viruses of hepatitis in which HBV & HCV are of great concern due to their high mortality and morbidity rate. HBV & HCV can be the reason for acute diseases and chronic diseases [16, 17]. Infections of HBV & HCV are a major health problem in the whole world as well as the main reason for morbidity & mortality in our country Pakistan [18]. WHO describes the presence of 350 million patients with infection of HBV with estimated deaths of about five lakhs sixty-three thousand per year and one hundred and seventy million patients with infection of HCV in the whole world with estimated deaths of 366000 per year [19]. Pakistan is a country which is seriously facing this trouble [20]. The transmission of HCV & HBV carried out in a consequence of direct contact of blood to blood, sharing of needles, sex with an infected person and from mother to the child [1]. There is a proof to declare that a large number of infections due to viruses in Pakistan have happened because of a large practice of the reuse of the needles [2]. Research Council of medical field has concluded in a research a decrease in the occurrence of hepatitis B & C to 2.5% & 4.9% correspondingly [3, 4]. There is still a requirement for great efforts to tackle this problem [4]. Transverse research works in USA, Puerto Rico, France & Norway have concluded relationship among various markers of SES & incidence of infection of HCV [5, 7]. No sufficient international, as well as national information, is present about the effect of economic and social condition on the increased occurrence of infections of hepatitis B & C.

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work carried out at Medicine Department of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from November 2016 to October 2017. All the patients of hepatitis B & C from all age groups and gender were the participants of this research work. Patients suffering from infections of other viruses or patients who were not willing to enter in the research work were not the part of this research work. Interview of all the participating patients conducted to know about the past history of operations, the previous history of needle pricking, tattooing, having shaved from barbers & transmitted risk features from the history of birth. The patients asked about their social and economic condition. The categorization of the social economic status carried out as poor, middle and upper classes in accordance with the monthly salary. A special organized Performa was in use to record the collected information. SPSS software was in use for the analysis of the information. Calculations of average and standard deviation carried out for quantitative variables as age of the patients & period of the disease. Application of Chi-square test carried out and a P value of <0.05 found as significant.

RESULTS:

There were two hundred patients in this case study, a large quantity of the patients was in the age group of thirty-one to forty-five years old, sixty-five patients were in the age group of forty-six to sixty years, and only twenty-five patients were in the age group of fifteen to thirty year. Male was one hundred and twenty and females were eighty. One hundred and five patients were from urban areas and ninety-five patients were from non-urban areas as described in Table – I.

Table – I: Patients Demographic characteristics

	Variables	Number	Percentage
Age	15-30 years	25	12.50
	31-45 years	110	55.00
	46-60 or > 60 years	65	32.50
	Total	200	100.00
Gender	Male	120	60.00
	Female	80	40.00
	Total	200	100.00
Residential Status	Rural	95	47.50
	Urban	105	52.00
	Total	200	100.00
Risk	Extra uses of needles/syringes	125	63.50

Factors	Barber shave	105	52.50
	Tattooing	10	5.00
	History of previous surgeries	30	15.00
	History of blood transfusion	24	12.50
	Unknown	50	25.00

In this study, all the male patients had the previous history of barber shaving & extra utilization of the syringes was very frequent in both genders making one hundred and twenty-five of the total population.

Thirty patients had the history of operations & twenty-four patients had the past of transfusion of blood. The amount of the factors with the amount of the patients is available in Table – II.

Table – II: Socioeconomic status of HBV and HCV Patients (200)

Viral Hepatitis		HCV	HBV	HCV+HBV	Total
Socioeconomic Status	Poor	71	18	7	96
	Middle	43	19	1	63
	Upper	28	10	3	41
Total		142	47	11	200
P-value		0.001	0.282	0.092	0.001

DISCUSSION:

The occurrence of hepatitis B & C is a dangerous health issue in poor countries & with low QOL (quality of life) [8]. In this research work, we found that poor social and economic class was mostly suffering from the infection of HCV making forty-eight percent of the total amount. Socioeconomic condition is not a direct factor of risk but it is the main reason behind many other risk aspects as poor patients from non-urban areas are not able to travel to far hospitals for medical treatment and they give preference to local practitioners where there is no availability of suitable medical treatment, in the same manner, pregnant females gave preference to local homes for maternity due to shortage of resources. Private hospitals are much far from the approach of poor patients.

In this research work, extra needles usage was very common in one hundred and twenty-five patients, thirty patients were present with previous histories of surgeries & twenty-four patients has passed of transfusion of blood and some females with cesarean surgery. Khan [9] concluded that two hundred and three patients left the local medical centres from non-urban population around Karachi. Khan J [10] concluded that sixty-seven percent patients had the previous record of transfusion of the blood. Sali [16] stated that the methods in the dental field conducted by other than dentists had enhanced the risk of HBV infection. Omland LH [12] concluded that there was a large quantity of the HCV patients in which fifty percent were the drug addicts through injections.

Janjua and Nizamy [13] carried out a transverse research work on barbers shaving in Rawalpindi and Islamabad & concluded that only thirteen percent barbers knew that this disease could be transmitted from blades of razors. Due to this factor, one hundred and twenty males and eighty females were the victims in which one hundred and five patients were from city areas and ninety-five were from village areas. Poor communities are mostly infected by the infections of HBV & HCV according to the outcome of this research work as forty-eight percent patients were from the lower class. SES (socioeconomic status) refers to the condition of the individual in his community or it may be on the basis of standards as qualifications, professions, salary & the norms of resident places [14]. Omland LH [12] showed that hepatitis C is more prevalent in the poor class. But this reason is still not clearly understood [20].

CONCLUSION:

Conclusions show that poor status associated with the incidence of the infection of hepatitis C. Social & economic condition is not a direct risk factor for the infections of hepatitis B & C, but it is the cause of the development of many other risk features. There is a need for the development of the procedures to handle the risk factors associated with the low social economic status to lower the burden of these diseases.

REFERENCES:

1. Ali SA, Donahue RM, Qureshi H, Vermund SH. Hepatitis B and hepatitis C in Pakistan: prevalence and risk factors. *International journal of infectious diseases*. 2009 Jan 1;13(1):9-
2. Last JM. *A Dictionary of Epidemiology*. 4th ed. New York: Oxford University Press; 2001
3. Meffre C, Le SY, Delarocque-Astagneau E, et al. Prevalence of hepatitis B and hepatitis C virus infections in France in 2004: social factors are important predictors after adjusting for known risk factors. *J Med Virol*. 2010; 82:546-555
4. Armstrong GL, Wasley A, Simard EP, McQuillan GM, Kuhnert WL, Alter MJ. The prevalence of hepatitis C virus infection in the United States, 1999 through 2002. *Ann Intern Med*. 2006; 144:705
5. Mukherjee PS, Dutta E, Das DK, Ghosh S, Neogi S, Sarkar A. Knowledge about hepatitis B and hepatitis C virus infection and consequences: a cross-sectional assessment of baseline knowledge among infected patients in West Bengal, India. *Hepatology, Medicine and Policy*. 2017 Dec;2(1):6;2-9
6. World Health Organization. Hepatitis B. World Health Organization Fact Sheet No. 204.2014. <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs204/en/>. Accessed Jul 2014
7. Khan J, Fida Z, Parvez A, Rafiq A, Syed S. Identifiable risk factors in hepatitis B and C. *Journal of Ayyub Medical College Abbottabad*. 2011 Dec 1 ;23(4):22-3.
8. Perez CM, Suarez E, Torres EA, Roman K, Colon V. Seroprevalence of hepatitis C virus and associated risk behaviours: a population-based study in San Juan, Puerto Rico. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2005; 34:593-599
9. Armstrong GL, Wasley A, Simard EP, McQuillan GM, Kuhnert WL, Alter MJ. The prevalence of hepatitis C virus infection in the United States, 1999 through 2002. *Ann Intern Med*. 2006; 144:705-714
10. Meffre C, Le SY, Delarocque-Astagneau E, et al. Prevalence of hepatitis B and hepatitis C virus infections in France in 2004: social factors are important predictors after adjusting for known risk factors. *J Med Virol*. 2010; 82:546-55
11. Ronie I. Economic and social factors fighting against hepatitis B and C contagion. *Romanian Journal of Economics*. 2015;40(1 (49)):184-93.
12. Khan AJ, Luby SP, Fikree F, Karim A, Obaid S, Dellawala S, et al. Unsafe injections and the transmission of hepatitis B and C in a periurban community in Pakistan. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2000; 78:956-63
13. Khan J, Fida Z, Parvez A, Rafiq A, Syed S. Identifiable risk factors in hepatitis B and C. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*. 2011 Dec 1;23(4):22-3.
14. Sali S, Bashir R, Alavian SM. Risk Factors in chronic hepatitis B infection: a case-control study. *Hepat Mon* 2005; 5: 109-115.
15. Omland LH, Osler M, Jepsen P, Krarup H, Weis N, Christensen PB, Roed C, Sorensen HT, Obel N. Socioeconomic status in HCV infected patients-risk and prognosis. *Clinical epidemiology*. 2013; 5:163.
16. Daud M, Hassan A, Ahmad A, Ali F, Khan MA, Rehman MU. Prevalence of Hepatitis B and C Infection in District Dir, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *World J Zool*. 2015;10(2):142-6.
17. Perz JF, Armstrong GL, Farrington LA, Hutin YJ, Bell BP. The contributions of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus infections to cirrhosis and primary liver cancer worldwide. *Journal of hepatology*. 2006 Oct 1;45(4):529-38.
18. Ali SA, Donahue RM, Qureshi H, Vermund SH. Hepatitis B and hepatitis C in Pakistan: prevalence and risk factors. *International journal of infectious diseases*. 2009 Jan 1;13(1):9-19

19. Kumar V, Abbas AK, Fausto N. Robbins and Cotran pathologic basis of disease. Elsevier Saunders. Philadelphia, PA. 2005:101.
20. Ahmed F. Multiplicity of Risk Factors for Chronic Viral Hepatitis B and C Infections in Pakistani Patients. SM J Hepat Res Treat. 2015; 1(1): 1001.
21. Pakistan Medical Research Council. National survey on the prevalence of hepatitis B and C in general population of Pakistan. 2010. Available from: www.pmrc.org.pk/hepatitisbc.html.